

EFFECT OF FIRM ATTRIBUTES ON FINANCIAL REPORTING LAG OF FINANCIAL FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The lack of timely release of financial information could make investors seek alternative sources of information. Consequently, this may affect the investment opportunity decision of the organization. This study looks at how firm factors affect financial reporting lag in Nigerian financial organizations. The population comprises of all forty-eight (48) quoted financial enterprises in Nigeria, with forty-two (42) firms serving as the sample size. Following diagnostic tests, the hypotheses were assessed with a random effect regression model. The findings revealed that business age has a considerable beneficial effect on financial reporting lag in Nigeria, but profitability has an insignificant positive effect on financial reporting lag. However, business size has no significant detrimental impact on the financial reporting lag of Nigerian financial organizations. The report suggests that long-established financial organizations engage large audit firms to audit their financial statements in order to lessen the delay in the delivery of audited financial statements in Nigeria. The study also suggests that Nigerian financial firms encourage large firm sizes to foster synergy, resulting in the prompt production of audited financial accounts in Nigeria. Finally, the report suggests that high-profit financial firms use large audit firms to examine their financial statements, thereby reducing the wait in the delivery of audited financial accounts in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Financial Reporting Lag; Financial Firms and Firm Attributes*

INTRODUCTION

Firm characteristics are internal elements that influence firm policy and decisions. They are the precise variables that increase the likelihood of reaching the firm's aim. Shehu, 2009 divides firm attributes into two groups: firm performance attributes and firm structural attributes. Firm performance attributes include firm growth and profitability, whereas firm structural features include business size, leverage, age, and management effectiveness. According to Suhaila et al. (2008), these characteristics separate one firm from another and influence the outcome of their performance. A firm's traits are those characteristics that are unique to the entity under audit. As a result, the qualities of firm age, company size, and profitability have been identified as independent factors in this study.

The years a business organization has existed is referred to as its firm age. Firm age is a property that is unique to each firm and varies among them. It is believed that established enterprises will submit their financial reports to the public considerably more quickly than newer ones, and that the available information will be able to assist the public in making economic decisions. It is considered that a firm's years of operation may influence the timeliness of its financial reporting. Previous study has suggested that older organizations may reveal their financial data to the public more quickly than younger companies.

Another element of significance is the firm's size, which is determined by its total assets. According to Modugu et al. (2012), the number of assets may reflect the amount of money owned by the firms. According to the research, business size is thought to have an impact on financial reporting timeliness because the larger the firm, the better the internal control system (Fodio et al., 2015) and is closely watched by interested parties (Dyer & Hugh, 1975).

Profitability refers to the firm's ability to produce a profit. This would be measured by referring to the firm's income statement, which reflects the performance of that particular firm.

Firms that are able to generate profitability are more likely to reveal financial results sooner to financial statement users in order to attract more investors and increase the favorable market value of their shares in the capital market. It is a good indicator for users of financial statements to make investment decisions. According to Apadore and Marjan (2013). Corporate companies are also obligated to create and communicate financial reports to shareholders and other interested parties at the conclusion of each fiscal year in order to facilitate optimal investment decision-making, among other things. Financial reporting is a critical tool for minimizing information asymmetry, which is the primary cause of poor investment decision-making.

One of the primary goals of corporate reporting is to give information that will aid internal and external users in making decisions. This information, however, must be made available within a short amount of time after the end of the reporting period; otherwise, the accounting information may lose its economic worth. Akingunola et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of publishing financial statements on time as required by statutory and regulatory requirements in order to boost investor confidence and make sound investment decisions. The requirement for timeliness raises and calls for the management of the reporting company and the auditor engaged to provide the audit and assurance services to be considerate of timeliness. For example, the profession of accounting and its respective users, regulatory and professional bodies, see to it that cutting down delays in audit is an improvement and touches on timeliness with regards to audit reports. Timely presentation of financial reports influences the decision-making process for an investor and other users.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of business qualities on financial reporting lag in Nigerian financial firms, which have frequently experienced financial crises in the past. Today's culture is very reactive to information, especially with the growth of technology, where platforms have been built to make it easier for stakeholders to obtain financial information. As a result, barriers to finance have been removed and market integration has improved, but volatility has also increased. Indeed, technical advancements have resulted in online trading platforms that lower capital flow obstacles and improve market competitiveness. As a result, the importance of submitting audit reports on time has grown.

Other studies concluded that financial reporting lag is bad news for investors because it increases the risk of fraudulent behavior (Rezaei & Shahroodi, 2015), whereas another group believes that long financial reporting lag is good news for investors because fraud can be detected with relative ease (Yim, 2010). Failure to release financial information on time may lead investors to seek alternative sources of information. This, therefore, can have an impact on the organization's investment opportunity decision. Thus, as Scott and Stanfield (2004) rightly argue and hold that "delayed financial information disclosure "might encourage Some unethical investors obtain pricey private pre-disclosure knowledge and, as a result, trade on it at the disadvantage of less informed investors." Leventis et al. (2005), on the other hand, stated that reporting delays allow for insider trading and the misappropriation or misapplication of business assets.

The weak financial reports play very strongly to one of the reasons investors are doubtful about the weak stock markets. Its risk is established through the inability to access information concerning the market situation, investee condition, and debts (Knechel et al., 2018). Information asymmetry has emerged as a result of the differences in managerial reports, therefore leading to conflict between managers and shareholders. Some companies like Axamansard Insurance, Niger Insurance Plc, Nigeria Energy Sector Fund and Universal Insurance Plc among others are still

reporting prolonged delays in their financial reporting which ought to aid stakeholders in their decisions making.

Most of the studies reviewed were sector-specific, covering industrial goods, consumer goods, insurance, and mining sectors. These studies reduce the generalizability of findings across different industries. There is very limited research into the timeliness of financial reporting across a more varied range of sectors to establish a broad understanding of what does and what does not impact reporting timeliness. Such studies were carried out in Indonesia and other different environments outside Nigeria, thereby creating a gap with regard to environmental differences. The results from these studies cannot be directly transferred into the Nigerian context given the differences in regulatory environments, economic conditions, and cultural factors. Research conducted within Nigeria using current data would fill that gap and make the findings more relevant.

Many studies adopted the purposive sampling method associated with bias and generalized results. There is room for random sampling methods to be conducted in order to ensure findings are representative and more widely applicable to firms in general. Quite a number of the studies were not based on recent data; periods used for analysis in most of the studies cut off as far back as 2017 or 2018. The nature of the business environment is such that it is very dynamic; therefore, more recent studies will be helpful in offering insights that can give the current perspective on what influences financial reporting timeliness. In regard to the methods used, some studies employed advanced techniques such as GMM or fixed effects modeling, while others employed basic statistical methods. This, in turn, provides scope for using more sophisticated econometric methods which can control endogeneity, and other complications of the data.

This study aims to examine the effect of firm attributes on financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria while the specific objectives are to: (i) determine the effect of firm age on financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria; (ii) evaluate the effect of firm size on financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria and (iii) examine the effect of profitability on financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria. Based on the specific objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are formulated in the null form to guide the study:

H₀₁: Firm age has no significant effect on financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria;

H₀₂: Firm size has no significant effect on financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria

and **H₀₃:** Profitability has no significant effect on financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Concept of Firm Attributes

Like many concepts, firm attributes are subject to different definitions, which emanate from individual peculiarities amongst firms and regulatory frameworks across different nations. In general, the differences in these definitions are accounted for by the disparities in the socio-economic, cultural, legal, and political settings of nations and the perspectives of the researchers. Firm attributes are referred to by Shehu and Farouk (2014) as those variables that are relatively persistent among different firms over any given period. According to Ali and Isa (2018), firm attributes are features that are unique to a firm and make it different from another firm. Firm attributes are features that make a corporate organization different from others, these include; firm size, leverage level, firm age, firm growth, and management efficiency among others. According to Maja et al., 2017, older aged firms are associated with experience in operations and management. Firm age is viewed as an incorporation length. Older firms tend to have a standard for most of the activities and well laid out policies for various aspects of operations. Older firms may perform better than the young firms due to the standard set for most of the activities and

well laid out policies for various aspects of operations. This paper has presented variables such as firm age, firm size, and profitability.

Firm Age

Claudio and Urs (2009) define a firm's age as the number of years after its listing or incorporation. Also, Claudio and Urs (2009) defined company age as the difference between a particular year of observation and the year of incorporation. Furthermore, Ofuan and Izien (2016) define solid age in two ways. The first refers to the number of years after the firm's initial listing, known as the listing age. The second definition, which is consistent with the definitions provided by Ofuan and Izien (2016) and Iyappan and Ganesamoorthy (2017), refers to firm age as the incorporation age, which is calculated as the number of years after the firm's incorporation date. There is a favorable correlation between age and financial statement timeliness (Soltani, 2002). This study defines firm age as the difference between the firm's incorporation date and the year of observation.

Firm Size

Shaheen and Malik (2012) defined firm size as the quantity and diversity of a firm's production capacity and capability, or the quantity and variety of services that a firm can provide to its consumers at the same time. Firm size refers to the rate and amount of expansion that is most appropriate for a specific firm. Most organizations want to expand their operations in order to increase revenues, profitability, staff numbers, or even facility size (Pervan & Visic, 2012).

Firm size is calculated as the natural logarithm of a firm's total assets, which may be easily regressed to determine the impact of total assets on performance (Driffield et al., 2005).

According to Ariani and Bawono (2018), firm size influences the pace of financial statement release since large organizations have enough internal controls that encourage auditors to conclude the audit process quickly. Many empirical researches have been undertaken based on firm size. Some utilized company size as a control variable, while others used it as a predictor variable in their research. Firm size is selected as the independent variable in this study since it is a proxy for firm traits. This study defines firm size as the natural logarithm of total assets for financial enterprises.

Profitability

Profitability reflects the management's performance in running the company. It also demonstrates the scale of a company's profitability as measured by several metrics such as operational income, net income, return on investment/assets, and rate of return on owner equity.” “Thus, profitability demonstrates a company's ability to generate profits. Profitability will influence the timeliness of financial reporting. High profitability indicates a firm's profits performance; it is a signal in the form of good news information. A corporation that has increased its profitability is likely to be more efficient in its audit process because it wants to rapidly send the signal, or good information, to the public and interested parties. The reality of profitability is that if it is high, there is a tiny chance of late financial report submission because the auditor does not need as much time to complete the audit for the company to submit its financial statements on time. This study defined profitability as a financial firm's annual profit divided by its total assets.

Financial Reporting Lag

Various authors have defined lag in financial reporting as the number of days between the end of the fiscal year and the date of the audit report. The reason for this is that the timeliness of audited annual reports is critical to investors, as it influences the value of information available to them when making investment decisions. Leventis et al. (2005) and Soltani (2002) contend that timely financial information and audit reports diminish information asymmetry and rumors

regarding a company's financial health. According to Jaggi and Tsui (1999), a timely audit report can improve a company's image by reducing investors' reliance on nontraditional avenues for information. The negative impacts of moral hazard and the consequences of adverse selection are mitigated as a result of timely financial information reporting (Leventis et al., 2005). According to Wisna (2013), this study defined financial reporting lag as the time between a company's fiscal year-end and the day the external auditors sign the financial statements.

Theory Underpinning the Study

Signaling Theory was propounded by Michael Spence in 1973. The theory primarily emerged out of Spence's work on the job market, where he showed how job applicants signal their abilities to the prospective employers through educational credentials.

Thrust of the Theory:

Signaling Theory: This theory holds that, in a case of information asymmetry between parties, individuals or entities will send signals to the other parties to communicate information. The signal is something associated with an action or attribute costly to acquire but credibly indicates some quality or characteristic. Signals in firms, such as financial reports, might convey the firms' operational efficiency, stability, and reliability to investors, regulators, and other relevant stakeholders.

Application to the Study: The Signaling Theory is utilized to explain how different corporate features can influence the timeliness of financial reporting in Nigeria.

- i. Firm age: If older organizations, with more years of market experience and established systems, can provide financial reports on time, this can be interpreted as an indication of stability and reliability. A shorter reporting lag would indicate that the company is well-established and capable of conducting efficient operations.
- ii. Firm Size: It stands to reason that the larger the firm, the more resources and structured processes one would expect to be in place to ensure that reporting happens on time. A short reporting time demonstrates operational efficiency and transparency, which are essential in sustaining investor confidence and the market reputation of the firm.
- iii. Profitability: Firms with good performance in profitability will have more incentives to report earlier to communicate good financial health to the market. Early reporting may convey that the firm is quite sure about its performance being good and indeed is very transparent.

Overall, the contribution of Signaling Theory to this study is to provide a framework for how attributes of the firm, like age, size, and profitability, may have a bearing on the financial reporting lag. Such timeliness may very well serve as a signal to markets about the underlying quality of the firm and its commitment to transparency and efficiency.

Empirical Review

Ihenyen et al. (2024) investigated the association between corporate characteristics and financial reporting timeliness among listed companies in Nigeria's industrial products industry. The cross-sectional analysis data included in the research spans the years 2013 to 2022, with business size and profitability identified as major factors of reporting timeliness. During data collection and analysis, an ex-post facto research approach was used, with multiple regression analysis carried out using Stata software. The population and sample included thirteen listed industrial goods companies from the Nigerian Exchange Group. Profitability had no significant effect on financial report timeliness, while business size had a considerable impact. The study made the following suggestions based on the above findings: Regulatory agencies should encourage enterprises to file annual reports on time, regardless of whether they are profitable or not in a given year. Despite the fact that the study adds to the current literature on the relationship between organizational qualities and financial reporting timeliness, there are several limitations. For

starters, because the study only looked at publicly traded industrial goods companies, its applicability to other industries is restricted. Second, one of the drawbacks is the purposeful sample technique, which limits the generalizability of the results across firms. Future research might benefit greatly from using random sampling to support their conclusions in terms of generalizability across industries.

Oyewole et al. (2024) Firm characteristics were evaluated in terms of their impact on timely financial disclosure in Nigerian insurance firms. This study examined reporting patterns over a twelve-year period, from 2009 to 2021. It focuses on how firm variables such as size and age affect the timeliness of financial reports, while also accounting for audit report delays. The study uses statistical approaches such as fixed effects modeling, diagnostic tests for data normality, and heteroskedasticity to create deep insights into financial reporting processes in Nigeria's insurance business. It was discovered that firm size has a statistically significant negative effect on the amount of timeliness in financial reporting practices; that is, larger organizations submit financial information more quickly. The association between firm age and reporting timeliness is also more complex and, hence, less straightforward, hinting those other forces may be at work. It will make practical recommendations to improve the integrity and efficiency of financial reporting in the Nigerian insurance business.

Terkende and Karim (2022) from 2017 to 2021, researchers investigated the impact of a firm's qualities on the timeliness of financial reporting on Nigerian listed consumer goods companies. The analysis was conducted on the entire population of consumer goods companies listed on the NGX Group for the subsample under consideration. Secondary data were acquired from sampled firms' annual reports, and the hypotheses were tested using the GLS regression analysis technique. The regression results show that firm size and financial leverage have a strong negative and substantial effect on the timeliness of financial reporting. According to the findings of this study, publicly traded consumer products companies may desire to expand their operations in order to reduce the time lag when reporting financial statements. Because the research is based on secondary data drawn from a single industry, generalizability is limited across a very short time period, 2017-2021. Research over a longer time period, incorporating additional company features, and possibly including comparative analysis with other sectors, will increase the findings' robustness and generalizability.

Lilik and Ani (2020) investigated the effect of profitability, solvency, company size, and public accounting firm repute on audit report latency. This study analyzed data from the annual reports of Indonesian listed mining companies from 2013 to 2017. The hypotheses were tested using the get method, which is multiple regression analysis. The findings demonstrated that, while profitability and scale have a considerable negative impact on audit report lag, solvency and reputation of the public accounting firm do not. The study suggests that future studies attempt to use methods other than the OLS approach, such as the Least Trimmed Squares method. Furthermore, this has ramifications for the study's currency, given it was completed in 2020 yet the data only covers up to 2017. The study was also repeated in another area outside of Nigeria previously, but the results cannot be generalized due to environmental differences. Also, the data must be updated to reflect the current period in Nigeria.

Rindi and Hadri (2020) assessed the effect of firm size, profitability, leverage, and opinion audit on audit delay in mining firms listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2014 to 2018, as well as whether audit quality could moderate firm size, profitability, leverage, and opinion audit rates on audit delay of mining firms listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange between 2014 and 2018. The study design utilized was quantitative. This study's population consists of all mining businesses registered on the Indonesian Stock Exchange over the five-year period 2014-2018. The gathered data were then analyzed using a double linear regression analysis model supported by the SPSS program version 20.00. The study found that audit delays are highly

influenced by profitability, leverage, and audit opinion, but not by firm size. Furthermore, quality auditing can minimize the effect of corporate size, profitability, and leverage on audit delay, however audit quality does not moderate the impact of audit opinions on audit delay. The study suggests adding more factors to the model. The survey was conducted in 2020, and the data only covered the years up to 2018, affecting the report's currency. The study was also conducted in a different context outside of Nigeria in the past, which cannot be generalized due to environmental changes and the necessity to update the data to reflect the present situation in Nigeria.

Trimisu et al. (2020) Investigated the impact of corporate attributes on auditors' reporting lag in Nigerian deposit money institutions. According to size, 10 listed banks were purposefully chosen, and essential data for the study were gathered from the sampled banks' financial reports from 2008 to 2017. The study used the dynamic generalized method of moment with a fixed effect to assess the effect of firm attributes on auditors' reporting lag. It discovers that age has a considerable beneficial effect on auditors' reporting lag in the tested bank, although size has no significant positive effect. However, changing profitability has a negative but non-significant effect on auditors' reporting latency. To reduce the reporting lag of Nigerian banks to auditors, the study recommended that banks have robust internal control mechanisms, accounting systems, and full compliance with all legislation, including accounting standards. The survey was conducted in 2020, however the data only goes back to 2017, which has a detrimental impact on the present nature of the study. The study was also conducted outside of Nigeria in the past, thus the environmental differences cannot be generalized, and the data must be updated to reflect the current period.

METHODOLOGY

This study used an ex post facto research design and focused on a sample of all forty-eight (48) financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of December 31, 2023. A sample of forty-two (42) financial enterprises was drawn from this population using defined criteria. To be included in the study, a company must have been listed on the NGX and operational between 2012 and 2023, as well as have the necessary data available in its financial statements throughout that time period. The essential data were acquired from the yearly financial reports of Nigeria's forty-two sampled financial firms. The study used a strong random effects model to evaluate the data and identify the link between the dependent and independent variables. To confirm the results' dependability, multiple robustness tests were performed, including the Shapiro-Wilk Normality Test, Pearson Correlation, Heteroscedasticity Test, and Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier Test.

The dependent variable in this study is the financial reporting lag, which is defined as the time between the end of the fiscal year and the date on which the external auditor signs the financial accounts of Nigeria's financial institutions. The independent variables are firm characteristics, notably firm age (FA), firm size (FSZ), and profitability (PRT). The functional relationship in the study is drawn from Terkende and Karim (2022), as follows:

$$FRL = f(FA + FSZ + PRT)$$

Econometrically, the model is stated thus:

$$FRL_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 FA_{it} + \beta_2 FSZ_{it} + \beta_3 PRT_{it} + e_{it} \text{-----Equation}$$

Where: β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are parameters estimated.

FRL = Financial Reporting Lag

FA = Firm Age

FSZ = Firm Size

PRT = Profitability

α = Constant

e = Error term

i = Firms

t = Periods

A-priori expectations: β_1, β_2 and $\beta_3 < 0$

Variables Measurement and Justification

Table 1: Variables Measurement and Justification

Variable	Acronym	Type	Measurement	Justification
Financial Reporting Lag	FRL	Dependent	This is the difference between a company's fiscal year-end and the day the external auditors sign the financial accounts.	Lilik and Ani (2020) and Oyewole et al. (2024).
Firm Age	FA	Independent	This is the distinction between the year of incorporation and the year 2021.	Trimisu <i>et al.</i> (2020) and Oyewole et al. (2024).
Firm Size	FSZ	Control Variable	This is a log of the total assets of financial firms in Nigeria.	Ihenyen et al. (2024) and Oyewole et al. (2024).
Profitability	PRT	Independent	Profit for the year/total assets.	Ihenyen <i>et al.</i> (2024), Lilik and Ani (2020) and Rindi and Hadri (2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data from forty-two (42) financial firms, covering the period from 2012 to 2023, were analyzed in this study. The variables included financial reporting lag (FRL), firm age (FA), firm size (FSZ), and profitability (PRT). The analysis was conducted using Stata 15 software, employing various statistical methods such as Descriptive Statistics, the Shapiro-Wilk Normality Test, Pearson Correlation, the Heteroscedasticity Test, the Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier, and the Robust Random Effects Regression Model.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 summarises the descriptive statistics of the entire data set.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
FRL	504	95.906	28.946	50	182
FA	504	41.971	17.361	20	103
FSZ	504	7.688	1.060	4.864	10.069
PRT	504	.008	0.094	-.562	0.291

Source: Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 software

Table 2 reveals that the financial reporting lag (FRL) varies from a minimum of 50 days to a maximum of 182 days, with an average (mean) value of 95.906 days falling within this range and representing a normal duration for the period investigated. FRL's standard deviation is 28.946 days, which is less than the mean, indicating a reasonably mild variance in reporting latency for the time under study. The table also shows that firm age (FA) has a minimum value of 20 years, a maximum value of 103 years, and a mean value of 41.971 years, indicating an average age within the studied period. The standard deviation for firm age is 17.361 years, which is less than the mean, implying a slow deviation in firm age over the review period.

Furthermore, Table 2 shows that firm size (FSZ) has a minimum value of 4.864, a maximum value of 10.069, and a mean value of 7.688, indicating an average size for the time period investigated. The standard deviation of 1.060 is less than the mean, indicating a progressive increase in company size over the time. Finally, profitability (PRT) is found to have a minimum value of -0.562, a maximum value of 0.291, and a mean value of 0.008, indicating an average across the analyzed range. The standard deviation of 0.094, which is larger than the mean, indicating that profitability fluctuated significantly throughout the time under study.

Shapiro Wilk Normality Test

Table 3 and Figure 2 show the results of the normality test using the Shapiro-Wilk Normality test and the normal distribution curve.

Variable	OBS	W	V	Z	Prob>Z
Residual	383	0.0634	0.1003	6.10	0.0474

Source: Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 software

Figure 2: Normal Distribution Curve

Table 3 reveals a residual value with a z value of 6.10 and a probability of 0.0474, which is less than 0.05, suggesting that the residuals are not normally distributed around the mean. Figure 2 depicts the normal distribution curve, which further supports this finding. This conclusion shows that one of the linear regression technique's key assumptions, namely normally distributed residuals, has been broken. To solve this issue, a robust regression technique was used.

Pearson Correlation

Table 4 The Pearson correlation matrix for the data set is shown below, demonstrating the extent of correlations between the variables.

Variable	FRL	FA	FSZ	PRT
FRL	1			
FA	0.1879	1		
FSZ	-0.1555	0.1001	1	
PRT	-0.0126	-0.0424	0.1437	1

Source: Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 software

The correlation matrix evaluates the strength of links between the independent variable proxies and the dependent variable, as well as if associations exist between the independent variable proxies themselves, in order to identify any multicollinearity concerns in the model. Table 4 shows an almost 19% positive and weak link between firm age (FA) and financial reporting lag (FRL) among Nigerian financial enterprises, with a correlation coefficient of 0.1879. The table also shows a roughly 15% negative and weak association between company size (FSZ) and financial reporting lag (FRL), with a correlation coefficient of -0.1555.

Furthermore, the table reveals a 1% negative and weak relationship between profitability (PRT) and financial reporting lag (FRL), with a correlation coefficient of -0.0126. The correlation coefficients between the independent variable proxies appear to be moderate, with all falling below Gujarati's (2003) 0.80 criteria. This means that the model has no multicollinearity, which satisfies one of the main requirements for linear regression.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Table 5: Heteroscedasticity test

Type of test	Chi2	P-Value
Heteroscedasticity Test	7.29	0.0069

Source: Researcher's Computation Using STATA 15 software

A heteroscedasticity test was performed to guarantee that the data utilized in this investigation was reliable. The results showed that the data had heteroscedasticity, which meant that the assumption of a basic linear regression model was broken. This is supported by the heteroscedasticity test result shown in Table 5, which has a chi-squared value of 7.29 and a p-value of 0.0069. This conclusion goes against the standard linear regression assumption of homoskedasticity, or constant error variance.

Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier

Table 6 below presents the result of the Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test conducted.

Variable	Chibar2	P-Value
FRL	55.93	0.000

Source: Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 software

The Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test was used to evaluate whether to utilize the Random Effect Model (REM) or Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Regression. The test results, as shown in Table 6, reveal a chibar2 value of 55.93 with a probability of 0.00, implying that the Random Effect Model is more appropriate than the Pooled OLS regression.

Results of the Robust Random Effect Regression Model

Table 7 below is the robust random effect regression model conducted for the estimation of this model.

Variable	Coefficients	z-value	Prob.
Cons.	108.818	5.83	0.000
FA	0.388	2.44	0.015
FSZ	-3.752	-1.60	0.110
PRT	8.405	0.50	0.620
R-sq overall	0.6509		
Wald chi2	7.81		
Prob. >chi2	0.0502		

Source: Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 software

Table 7 The combined influence of Firm Age (FA), Firm Size (FSZ), and Profitability (PRT) accounts for 65% of the variation in financial reporting lag (FRL), as evidenced by the Overall R-squared value of 0.6509. This indicates that the independent variables are effectively used in the model. Furthermore, the Wald chi-squared value of 7.81 with a P-value of 0.0502 indicates that the model is adequate and well-suited to the investigation.

Test of Hypotheses

To investigate the impact of firm qualities on the financial reporting lag of financial firms in Nigeria, the study tested the following hypotheses using a random effect regression model:

Firm Age

Table 7 demonstrates that, with a z-value of 2.44 and a matching p-value of 0.015, company age had a substantial beneficial effect on the financial reporting lag of Nigerian financial enterprises over the period under study. As a result, the first null hypothesis, which held that firm age had no substantial effect on financial reporting lag, was rejected.

Firm Size

Table 8 indicates a z-value of -1.60 and a p-value of 0.110, implying that firm size has no significant negative impact on financial reporting latency. As a result, the second null hypothesis, namely that firm size has no substantial effect on financial reporting latency, is accepted.

Profitability

Further results in Table 8 reveal a z-value of 0.50 and a p-value of 0.620, indicating that profitability has an insignificant beneficial influence on financial reporting latency. Thus, the third null hypothesis, implying that profitability has no meaningful effect on financial reporting latency, is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The study discovered that business age considerably increases financial reporting lag (coefficient = 0.388). This finding defies the researcher's initial expectations and is inconsistent with signaling theory, which states that firm characteristics such as age should influence the timeliness of financial reporting as a signal of the firm's quality and commitment to transparency. This result is also consistent with Lilik and Ani (2020) and Rindi and Hadri (2020). However, this conclusion is congruent with those of Ihenyen et al. (2024).

The study indicates that firm size has an insignificant negative impact on financial reporting lag, reducing it by -3.752. This finding aligns with the researcher's initial expectations and is consistent with signaling theory, as larger firms are expected to signal their commitment to transparency and efficiency through timely financial reporting. This result is also in agreement with Rindi and Hadri (2020) but contrasts with the findings of Ihenyen, Ojiaku, Naagi, and Agagowei (2024), Oyewole et al. (2024).

The study shows that profitability has an insignificant positive effect on financial reporting lag, increasing it by 8.405. This finding does not align with the researcher's initial expectations or with signaling theory, which would suggest that more profitable firms would report more promptly as a signal of their financial health. The result is consistent with the findings of Ihenyen et al. (2024) but diverges from the findings of Lilik and Ani (2020), Rindi and Hadri (2020).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The older a company is, the longer it takes to release audited financial results to Nigerian customers. Financial institutions with a long history are more likely to postpone the publishing of their audited financial statements, potentially affecting the quality of investment decisions made by users of these statements. In contrast, the larger a corporation, the faster it tends to produce its

audited financial records, hence improving the quality of investment decisions for Nigerian users. However, as a company's profitability improves, so does the time it takes to release audited financial accounts. Financial firms with bigger profit margins may delay the release of audited financial statements, lowering the quality of investment decisions for Nigerians.

Based on the above conclusion, the following recommendations are provided:

- (i) Long-standing financial firms should hire large audit firms to speed up the release of audited financial accounts in Nigeria.
- (ii) Financial firms in Nigeria should encourage large firm size to foster synergy, resulting in the timely release of audited financial accounts in Nigeria.
- (iii) High-profit corporations should hire large audit firms to speed up the release of audited financial accounts in Nigeria.

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